

The influence of Employees' engagement on Career success: A Case study of Buddhist Temple in Guangdong Province, China

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Abstract:

The personnel management of Buddhist temples outlines the personnel management pattern of temples, which is based on the premise of firm Buddhist belief, relying on the development of temple economy, supported by the cultivation of strong team spirit, and focusing on the cultivation of excellent executive ability and learning ability. Since the era of knowledge economy, people pay more and more attention to career success, and the standard of career success is more and more diversified. Career success is a person's positive psychological or work-related achievements or achievements accumulated in the process of career development. There are many influencing factors, including personal level and organizational level. Employee engagement is an important influencing factor of career success. The purpose of this study is to explore the influence mechanism of Buddhist temple employee engagement on career success in Guangdong Province. Therefore, based on the extended construction theory, this study introduces employee performance into the model, and constructs a theoretical model of the relationship between employee engagement and career success and employee performance. This study takes the employees of 1552 Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province as the research object; collects data by questionnaire survey, and a total of 307 valid questionnaires are collected; uses structural equation model for analysis. The results show that employee engagement has a significant impact on career success and employee performance. According to the above research conclusions, this paper puts forward corresponding suggestions for the personnel management of Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province.

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INTRODUCTION

In many areas of China, because of the wide range of religious beliefs, religious temples are not only widely distributed, numerous, but also play a very important role. Between religion and believers, religious life and secular life, religious influence and state management, religious temples are undoubtedly an important and stable medium. Paying attention to the management of religious temples means that the religious management has a solid foothold (Liu, 2018). Especially in ethnic areas, the management of religious temples is almost equal to the management of society, the management of the people, the management of life, the management of stability and the management of culture. At present, the events involving religious temples, especially some events with great influence, increase on one hand, it shows the expansion of influence of religious temples, on the other hand, it shows the importance of strengthening the management of religious temples in all aspects, and puts forward new requirements for innovation of management methods in various aspects of religious temples. The management of religious temples involves many contents, such as management subject, management mode, management content, management objective and management personnel. On the one hand, it involves the state, religion, religious organization, religious organization, religious personnel and the general public, involving various subjects; on the other hand, it also involves various affairs such as politics, economy, culture, law and diplomacy, involving various social relations (Zaxi, 2018). What means, how to manage and achieve what kind of purpose, we must base on new understanding and get new answers. With the development and change of society, the human resource management mode of religious temples should keep pace with the times.

Buddhism is imported from India, and its development history in China has exceeded 1900 years. In fact, Buddhist temples are organizations with a long history and strong vigor. The reason why Buddhist temples are so popular is curious. On the other hand, in recent years, there are three typical cases of negative news about Buddhist temples. First, in 2006, the prior of temple A was promoted to abbot without permission of the Buddhist Association. Results in the process of investigation, it was found that there were families outside, which indicated that some Buddhist monks' beliefs were shaken, and there were crises in human resource management and organizational culture management. Second, at the end of 2011, "Southern Weekend" reported that the chief of temple B was a suspected murderer who had been hiding for 15 years (currently sentenced), which made people wonder that the entrance control of Buddhist monks was too loose and the human resource management was not strict enough. Third, during the Spring Festival in 2012, temple C, a national 5A scenic spot, is in danger of being delisted by the National Tourism Administration because of its over commercialization.

Under the impact and baptism of globalization, all traditions, including their derivatives, are faced with the challenge of "transformation" or "reconstruction". The inherent ideas and ideas need to be updated and transformed, and the original practices and methods are faced with the situation of "reorganization" or even "destruction" (You, 2019). For all traditions, it may only be the things that are too "out of date" that gradually disappear. In addition, the factors that have been tested and precipitated can be said to be lasting and new. In a sense, globalization provides the impetus and opportunity for traditional "transformation" and renewal. Tradition can be innovated and reborn through "transformative creation", and it is more vigorous than before. The research group of provincial and ministerial cadres of the Central Party school went to Guangdong after a comprehensive investigation of many management modes including human resource management of Buddhist temples in the province. Mr. Jiang Jianyong, deputy group leader, also expressed his deep feeling that "the institutionalization, standardization and scientization of temple management in Guangdong

Province is refreshing, which has won the general praise of believers and explored the way for the management of secular Buddhist temples, which is worthy of affirmation" (Xian, 2012).

Problem Statement

The purpose of this study is to promote and improve the management level of Buddhist affairs and business enterprises in Guangdong Province by using the accommodation and mutual borrowing of religious affairs and business management principles, which will contribute to the construction of a harmonious society. In the framework of national governance and building a harmonious society, the management of major systems and their subsystems are organically linked. Business Administration and religious (Buddhist) affairs management belong to the two important systems of national governance and social public management. This study mainly discusses the important module of human resource management in the field of business administration. It aims to explore the impact of staff engagement on their career success in Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province, and take performance as an intermediary factor.

The significance of business enterprise management begins with the exchange of surplus material products in primitive society, and then is the gradual management after the emergence of orderly production, processing and trading. It has been revolutionary since its emergence, and directly affects the construction of a specific economic society, the evolution of politics and the direction of culture (Luo and Feng, 2002). Compared with the stability of religious (Buddhist) affairs management, the significant difference lies in the activity and dispersion contained in the revolution of business management. Absorbing the experience of business administration in the management of religious (Buddhist) affairs will contribute to the sustainable coordination and adaptation of religion and society, and the development of Buddhism with the times. All these will help to promote the construction and continuation of a harmonious society, and provide a solid political, economic, cultural and social security foundation for the realization of the "Chinese dream" (Deng, 2015). Through several years' study of doctor of business administration, the author has expanded his vision. On the basis of the original basic research, the author tries to use the relevant principles and knowledge and methods of business management to conduct a more in-depth study on strengthening and optimizing the personnel management of Buddhist organizations in Guangdong Province, which will provide more reference for other scholars. The current study includes the two research questions: (i) what is the status of personnel management in Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province? and (ii) what are the factors that affect the professional engagement of Buddhist temple personnel in Guangdong Province? and addresses the two objectives: (i) understand the status quo of the management of Buddhist temple staff in Guangdong Province, and (ii) explore the influencing factors of the variables influencing the employee engagement, employee performance and career success of Buddhist temple staff in Guangdong Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dependent Variables: Career Success

The western academic research on career success began in the 1930s, but there were not many scholars engaged in this research at that time. With the gradual deepening of the research on the concepts related to occupation and people's increasing attention to mental health, the research on career success has developed rapidly in the West. Thorndike (1934) was the first to carry out the relevant research on career success. He defined career success operationalization as job satisfaction. Hunt, Chonko and Wood (1986) divided career success into objective (external) and subjective (internal). Career success refers to the verifiable and

observable value achievements in the process of career development. Its external standards mainly include salary level and promotion times, which are often based on others' evaluation. In addition, Seibert and Kraimer (2001) defined career success as a person's positive psychological or work-related achievements or achievements accumulated in the process of career development. Nigel Nicholson et al. (2005) made a more in-depth discussion on the criteria of objective career success.

Measurement of career success

At present, most researchers use the five item career satisfaction questionnaire developed by Greenhaus (1990). The four item scale developed by Huang (2003) is also a commonly used tool to measure subjective career success. In addition, Huang (2003) evaluated their salary, welfare, the satisfaction of their superiors and colleagues, and then calculated the total score to get the job satisfaction level, so as to measure their career success. Eby, Butts and Lockwood (2003) proposed that psychological indicators (mainly job satisfaction) and objective indicators (such as labor market competitiveness) should be used as comprehensive career success indicators. In the era of knowledge economy, the standard of career success has changed, and individual mobility is regarded as an important standard of career success. According to Arthur et al. (2005), besides subjective and objective success, career success should also include Inter Organizational mobility and extra organizational career support. Therefore, there are three criteria to measure career success: personal career satisfaction, perceived internal competitiveness and perceived external competitiveness. The standard replaces the traditional salary and promotion with competitiveness index, which not only emphasizes the role of subjective success standard, but also combines subjective factors with objective factors, and reduces the disadvantages of traditional standard, which is more in line with the characteristics of the development of the times. Therefore, it has become a new standard of career success in the era of knowledge economy.

Employee engagement

Kahn (1990) first put forward the concept of employee engagement. He believed that employee engagement is the degree of employees' involvement in the work role and the process of combining self role and work role. Employee engagement refers to the emotional, cognitive and personal accomplishment of their work and self-expression in it. However, although Kahn provides a conceptual basis for engagement, the operational definition is not given. Subsequent scholars continue to join in, to explore the concept of engagement, through theoretical construction and empirical analysis will lead the concept of engagement to depth. Maslach and Leiter (1999) extended Kahn's definition of engagement from the perspective of job burnout. They think that engagement should be regarded as the opposite of job burnout, which is two different extremes in the same state with job burnout, and define employee engagement as the opposite of job burnout. For example, job burnout is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment. Its characteristics are high energy, devotion and high efficiency.

The structural dimension of employee engagement

The components of employee engagement are multidimensional. Foreign scholar Kahn (1990) divides employee engagement into three dimensions: physiological engagement, cognitive engagement and emotional engagement. Maslach et al. (1997) divided employee engagement into three dimensions: energy, involvement and self-efficacy. Rothbard et al. (2001) divided employee engagement into two dimensions: attention and total engagement. Schaufeli et al. (2002) believe that employee engagement includes three dimensions: vigor, dedication and concentration. Paul and Rich (2006) believe that employee engagement includes three dimensions: behavioral engagement, cognitive engagement and emotional

engagement. Domestic scholar Zha (2007) divides employee engagement into three dimensions: work engagement, organizational identity and work value. Yang (2012) divides employee engagement into three dimensions: devotion to work, identification with work and pursuit of development. Zeng and Han (2015) divided employee engagement into six dimensions: task center, vigor, active participation, value internalization, sense of efficacy and positive support.

Employee engagement and employee performance

According to Kahn (1990), employee engagement refers to the combination of self and work role. Self and role are a dynamic and harmonious relationship. In job role play, employees can employ themselves and express themselves at different levels of physiology, cognition and emotion. In the work role, when employees are highly engaged, they will identify with the performance of the work role physically, cognitively or emotionally; when employees are not engaged, they will put themselves out of the work role to avoid the performance they need to create the work role. A large number of empirical studies have shown that employee engagement has a significant impact on employee performance (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti and Schaufeli, 2009; Bakker and Bal, 2011) and happiness (Xanthopoulou, Bakker and Lilies, 2012). Employee engagement is positively correlated with individual work performance (Xantholoulou et al., 2012), situational performance (organizational citizenship behavior and off role performance) (Christian, Garza and Slougher, 2013), positive behavior (Sonnetag and Sabine, 2013), personal work family promotion (Culbertson, Mills and Fullagar, 2014), and subjective well-being. Employee engagement is positively correlated with in role performance and out of role performance (Halbesleben and Wheeler, 2014; Bakker et al., 2016), business unit performance (Harter, Schmidt and Hayes, 2014) and customer satisfaction (Salanova, Agut and Peiro, 2015). He (2015) has proved that job engagement is not only positively correlated with individual job performance, but also can better predict the status of job performance; employee engagement will have a positive impact on work attitude, job performance and even organizational performance (Chen and Shen, 2015; Chen, Liu and Shen, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, the management theory is applied to the management of religious Buddhist monasteries. Guided by social exchange theory, extended construction theory, career construction theory, human resource management theory and Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, this study aims to build and use the index system of employee engagement and career success. Based on the analysis of literature and previous academic achievements, this paper preliminarily determines the measurement indicators of the relationship between employee engagement and career success, and transforms these indicators into the form of questionnaire, issues questionnaire and collects data, and uses spss22.0 statistical software to carry out exploratory factor analysis on the data and revise the indicators. On this basis, by issuing the questionnaire again and collecting the data, using amos24.0 statistical software to carry out confirmatory factor analysis on the data to test the fit of the questionnaire, and through the reliability and validity test, finally constructed the enterprise performance management employee satisfaction measurement index system. Finally, based on the analysis of 1552 Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province since 2015, this paper makes an empirical analysis, and carries out questionnaire distribution and data collection for temple employees, and carries out factor analysis on the collected data. Finally, through calculation, the comprehensive results of the impact of Buddhist temple employee engagement on career success in Guangdong Province are obtained. Based on the current personnel management

mode in Guangdong Province, combined with the comprehensive score of the impact of employee engagement on career success and the score of employee performance as the intermediary factor index, the author puts forward some suggestions and Countermeasures for improving the personnel management of Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province. It includes: giving full play to the role of leadership, that is, the management takes the lead in setting an example; nurturing combat effectiveness, that is, coordinating the management order of the hierarchical organization of Buddhist temples; building executive capacity, that is, promoting the smooth instructions of Buddhist temples; cultivating cohesion, that is, paying attention to the team spirit of monks; and implementing Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory in the personnel management of Buddhist temples. See Figure 3-1 for details.

Figure 3-1 Research design

Population/Sampling/Unit of Analysis

This paper studies the influence of Buddhist temple staff engagement on career success in Guangdong Province. Therefore, the population involved in the study is all the staff of Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province, including monastic members and lay disciplines. In this study, all employees of 1552 Buddhist monasteries in Guangdong Province were selected, and 307 employees were collected by questionnaire survey. In order to meet the randomness requirements of the sample, the subjects of this survey are designed in many areas of Guangdong Province, including Shenzhen, Guangzhou, Chaozhou, Zhaoqing, Shaoguan, Meizhou and Yunfu etc.. Specifically, 400 questionnaires were distributed in this study, and 336 questionnaires were collected, with a recovery rate of 84%. The researchers then screened the questionnaires, and eliminated the invalid questionnaires with seven or more

answers in a row and the same option, and some of the answers in the questionnaire were missing, and 307 valid questionnaires were recovered. Therefore, the effective rate of the questionnaire is 91.4%. The unit of analysis defines what is being studied in this study and is the entity being studied as a whole. In this study, the unit of analysis is the whole organization of Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province.

Instrumentation

In order to facilitate data analysis, Likert seven point scoring method was used for all scales in this questionnaire, from 1 to 7, representing "very disagree", "disagree", "relatively disagree", "general (neutral)", "relatively agree", "agree" and "very agree".

(1) Employee engagement scale

In the measurement of employee engagement, we use the UWEs scale developed by schaufeli et al. (2002), which contains 17 items and is divided into three dimensions: vigor, dedication and absorption. The reliability of the original scale is 0.93, using Likert's seven point scoring method, 1 = very disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = relatively disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = relatively agree, 6 "agree", 7 "very agree".

(2) Employee performance scale

In this study, the employee performance scale adopted by Tusi et al. (1997) is used to measure employee performance. Employee performance is divided into two dimensions, namely, basic task performance and organizational citizenship behavior, including 11 items and 9 items respectively, which are evaluated by employees themselves. The first six items of basic task performance are used to evaluate the extent to which employees agree that they are superior to other colleagues in terms of quantity, quality and efficiency in completing core work tasks; the last five items are used to measure employees' overall ability, judgment, accuracy, work knowledge and creativity in completing core work tasks. The validity of the original scale was 0.60 and 0.67 respectively. The scale adopts Likert's seven point scoring method, which is 1 = very disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = relatively disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = relatively agree, 6 "agree", 7 "very agree".

(3) Career success scale

In this study, Wang and Long (2009) was used to translate, evaluate and revise the occupational competitive power scale compiled by Eby et al. (2003) and the occupational satisfaction scale compiled by Greenhaus (1990). There are two subscales: perceived internal competitiveness and perceived external competitiveness, which contain three items respectively. The career satisfaction scale is a one-dimensional scale with five items. The original reliability of the questionnaire was 0.739, 0.753 and 0.854, respectively. The career satisfaction scale developed by greenhaus (1990) is widely used to evaluate career success. The questionnaire adopts Likert's seven point scoring method, which is 1 = very disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = relatively disagree, 4 = neutral, 5 = relatively agree, 6 "agree", 7 "very agree".

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of Respondents

In this study, the researchers selected the staff of Buddhist temples in Guangdong Province as population. The results of descriptive statistical analysis of the basic information of the respondents are as follows:

(1) Gender distribution

Table 4-1 Gender distribution of respondents

Variable	Item	No. of People	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	206	67.10%
	Female	101	32.90%
	Total	307	100.00%

Source: Author

Table 4-1 shows the results of descriptive statistical analysis on the gender of the sample. The data shows that among the 309 Temple employees surveyed, 206 are male employees, accounting for 67.1%; 101 are female employees, accounting for 32.9%. The proportion of male and female employees is about 2:1, with male employees in the majority.

(2) Age distribution

Table 4-2 Age distribution of respondents

Variable	Item	No. of People	Percentage (%)
Age	Less than 25 years old	39	12.70%
	26-30 years old	76	24.76%
	31-40 years old	90	29.32%
	41-50 years old	85	27.69%
	51-60 years old	15	4.89%
	More than 60 years old	2	0.65%
	Total	307	100.00%

Source: Author

Table 4-2 shows the results of descriptive statistical analysis on the age of the sample. The table shows that the age distribution of the sample is relatively wide. Among them, 90 employees aged 31-40 years old accounted for 29.32%, followed by 85 employees aged 41-50 years old, accounting for 27.69%, and 76 employees aged 25-30 years old, accounting for 24.76%. The total proportion of employees in these three age groups is 81.77%, indicating that most of the sample employees are 26-50 years old, which is consistent with the actual situation. In addition, there are 39 employees under 25 years old, accounting for 12.70%; 15 employees between 51 and 60 years old, accounting for 4.89%; and 2 employees over 60 years old, accounting for 0.65%.

Analysis on Research Objective 1

Table 4-8 shows the descriptive statistical analysis results of each variable and its dimensions in this study. The average value of career success variable is 5.1756; among them, the average value of perceived internal competitiveness dimension is 5.0793, the average value of perceived external competitiveness dimension is 5.1699, and the average value of career satisfaction dimension is 4.6708. The mean value of employee performance variable is 5.5062; the mean value of basic task performance dimension is 5.5304, and the mean value of organizational citizenship behavior dimension is 5.4798. Finally, the mean value of employee engagement variable is 5.4613; among them, the mean value of vigor dimension is 5.5016, the mean value of dedication dimension is 5.4947, and the mean value of absorption dimension is 5.3962.

Table 4-3 Descriptive statistical analysis results of each variable and its dimension

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Perceived internal competitiveness	307	1.00	7.00	5.0793	0.706
Perceived external competitiveness	307	1.33	7.00	5.1699	0.653
Job satisfaction	307	0.45	5.27	4.6708	0.290
Career success	306	1.45	7.00	5.1756	0.553
Basic task performance	307	2.36	7.00	5.5304	0.476
Organizational citizenship behavior	305	2.00	7.00	5.4798	0.537
Employee performance	305	2.30	7.00	5.5062	0.457
Vigor	305	1.00	7.00	5.5016	0.644
Dedication	307	1.00	7.00	5.4947	0.636
Absorption	306	1.00	7.00	5.3962	0.614
Employee engagement	307	1.00	7.00	5.4613	0.601

Source: Author

Results

The data shows that the average value of all variables except job satisfaction is above 5, which indicates that employees' feelings on these variables are in the upper middle level. It is worth noting that the average of career satisfaction is only 4.6708, which indicates that the level of career satisfaction of employees is not high.

Analysis on Research Objective 2: Influencing Factors

(1) Employee engagement

Employee engagement consists of three latent variables, vigor, dedication and absorption. Among them, vigor has six measurement indexes, dedication has five measurement indexes, and absorption has six measurement indexes. The confirmatory factor analysis model is shown in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-1 Confirmatory factor analysis model of employee engagement

Source: Author

The validity indexes of the confirmatory factor analysis model of employee engagement are shown in Table 4-9.

Table 4-4 Results of validation factor analysis of employee engagement model

Index	Factor load (normalized regression coefficient λ)	Reliability λ^2	Measurement error $1-\lambda^2$	CR	AVE
VI1	0.723	0.523	0.477	0.8877	0.5689
VI4	0.744	0.554	0.446		
VI8	0.802	0.643	0.357		
VI12	0.726	0.527	0.473		
VI15	0.788	0.621	0.379		
VI17	0.739	0.546	0.454		
DE2	0.752	0.566	0.434	0.8775	0.5894
DE5	0.738	0.545	0.455		
DE7	0.782	0.612	0.388		
DE10	0.824	0.679	0.321		
DE13	0.739	0.546	0.454		
AB3	0.523	0.274	0.726	0.8584	0.5067
AB6	0.720	0.518	0.482		
AB9	0.684	0.468	0.532		
AB11	0.774	0.599	0.401		
AB14	0.808	0.653	0.347		
AB16	0.727	0.529	0.471		

Source: Author

According to the data in Table 4-9, the CR value of vigor dimension is 0.8877, and the AVE value is 0.5689. The CR value of the dedication dimension is 0.8775, and the AVE value is 0.5894. The CR value of the absorption dimension is 0.8584 and the AVE value is 0.5067.

(2) Employee performance

Employee performance consists of two latent variables: basic task performance and organizational citizenship behavior. Among them, there are 11 measurement indicators of basic task performance and 9 measurement indicators of organizational citizenship behavior. The confirmatory factor analysis model of employee performance is shown in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-2 Confirmatory factor analysis model of employee performance
 Source: Author

Table 4-5 Results of confirmatory factor analysis of employee performance model

Index	Factor load (normalized regression coefficient λ)	Reliability λ^2	Measurement error $1-\lambda^2$	CR	AVE
BTP1	0.75	0.4225	0.5775		
BTP2	0.77	0.4489	0.5511		
BTP3	0.67	0.4489	0.5511		
BTP4	0.66	0.4356	0.5644		
BTP5	0.65	0.4225	0.5775		
BTP6	0.68	0.4624	0.5376	0.9176	0.5044
BTP7	0.78	0.6084	0.3916		
BTP8	0.77	0.5929	0.4071		
BTP9	0.75	0.5625	0.4375		
BTP10	0.68	0.4624	0.5376		
BTP11	0.63	0.3969	0.6031		
OCB12	0.71	0.5041	0.4959		
OCB13	0.73	0.5329	0.4671		
OCB14	0.66	0.4356	0.5644		
OCB15	0.78	0.6084	0.3916		
OCB16	0.74	0.5476	0.4524	0.9116	0.5349
OCB17	0.82	0.6724	0.3276		
OCB18	0.73	0.5329	0.4671		
OCB19	0.71	0.5041	0.4959		
OCB20	0.69	0.4761	0.5239		

Source: Author

(1) Career success

Career success consists of three latent variables: perceived internal competitiveness, perceived external competitiveness and career satisfaction. There are three measurement indicators of perceived internal market competitiveness, three measurement indicators of perceived external market competitiveness and five measurement indicators of career satisfaction. The second-order confirmatory factor analysis model of career success is shown in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-3 second order confirmatory factor analysis model of career success
Source: Author

Table 4-6 Results of confirmatory factor analysis of career success model

Index	Factor load coefficient λ	(normalized regression Reliability coefficient λ^2	Measurement error $1-\lambda^2$	CR	AVE
CS1	0.881	0.7762	0.2238	0.8598	0.6722
CS2	0.783	0.6131	0.3869		
CS3	0.792	0.6273	0.3727		
CS4	0.672	0.4516	0.5484	0.8185	0.6025
CS5	0.800	0.6400	0.3600		
CS6	0.846	0.7157	0.2843		
CS7	0.653	0.4264	0.5736	0.856	0.545
CS8	0.686	0.4706	0.5294		
CS9	0.729	0.5314	0.4686		
CS10	0.833	0.6939	0.3061		
CS11	0.770	0.5929	0.4071		

Source: Author

According to the data in Table 4-15, among the variables of career success, the CR value of perceived organizational internal competitiveness index is 0.8598 and AVE value is 0.6722; the CR value of perceived organizational external competitiveness index is 0.8185 and AVE value is 0.6025; the CR value of career satisfaction index is 0.856 and AVE value is 0.545.

Table 4-15 shows the fitting index of the second-order confirmatory factor analysis model of career success.

The main purpose of confirmatory factor analysis is to analyze the degree of each factor fitting the actual data based on the previous exploratory factor analysis, so as to judge whether the number of factors and factor load of the observed variables can be consistent with the expected theory (Kong and Ding, 2014). Therefore, on the premise that exploratory factor analysis has obtained the factor structure, a confirmatory factor analysis model is established to test whether the data work according to the predetermined factor structure by taking the dimensions derived from the theory as the observation variables (Li and Huang, 2017). Therefore, through exploratory factor analysis to build employee engagement and career success measurement index system, through the collection of data, using confirmatory factor analysis to verify, the differences between the factor structure and the observed variables are compared, in order to test whether the factor structure proposed before has fitness. In this study, the researchers analyzed the degree of each factor fitting the actual data through confirmatory factor analysis to determine whether each factor structure in employee engagement, employee performance and career success has fitness. Through confirmatory factor analysis, it can be concluded that three factors (vigor, dedication and absorption) influencing employee engagement variables are established, which are consistent with previous scholars' research results (May, 2004; Zha, 2007; Briscoe and Hall, 2015; Wang and Zhang, 2015). Secondly, basic task performance and organizational citizenship behavior constitute two dimensions of influencing employee performance variables, which enrich previous academic research results (Baker and Bal, 2011; Culbertson, Mills and Fullagar, 2014; Halbesleben and Wheeler, 2014). Finally, the factors influencing career success are composed of perceived internal competitiveness, perceived external competitiveness and career satisfaction, which are in line with the research results of previous scholars (Nigel, 2005; Zha, 2007; Niu, 2009; Liu, 2013).

CONCLUSION

In this paper, in the process of studying the impact of Buddhist temple employee engagement on career success in Guangdong Province, due to the lack of relevant research, we need to comb a large number of literature to support the hypothesis. In the process of empirical test, this paper attempts to use structural equation modeling method for empirical research. On the basis of theoretical research and empirical test, relevant management suggestions are put forward. Due to my limited level and the relatively complex theoretical model, the operability of the suggestions on the relationship between employee engagement and career success mediated by employee performance also needs to be discussed. However, this paper analyzes the impact of Buddhist temple staff engagement on career success in Guangdong Province, not a simple theoretical overview, but through statistical description and comparative analysis, so as to understand the research problems and research objectives more thoroughly. Secondly, when testing the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, factor analysis can be used to find out whether employee engagement has an impact on career success. Finally, this study confirms that employee performance partially mediates, rather than completely mediates, which is one of the highlights of this paper.

REFERENCES

- Adelien, D.. (2013). Carine Smolders, Alex Vanderstraeten. Employee performance management culture and system features in higher education: relationship with employee performance management satisfaction. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(2), 352-371.
- An, K. J.. (2018). Research on human resource management from the perspective of sharing

- economy. *Financial information*, (24), 195.
- Arham A. (2011). *Evaluation of Job Satisfaction and Performance of Employees in Small and Medium Sized Construction Firms in Nigeria*. International Economics Development and Research Center(IEDRC). The Proceedings of 2011 2nd International Conference on Construction and Project Management.
- Arthur, M.B., Khapova, S.N., & Wilderom, C.P.M.. (2005). Career success in Boundaryless Career World. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, (26), 177-202.
- Bai, X. Y., Zhang, S. Y., Guo, Y. Y., Zhang, Y. Q., Liu, X. W., & Wei, J.. (2020). The influence of individual achievement motivation on the Overwork of professional women. *Management observation*, (5), 76-79.
- Bakker, A. B. , & Bal, M. P.. (2011). Weekly work engagement and performance: a study among starting teachers. *Journal of Occupational & Organizational Psychology*, 83.
- Bakker, A. B. , Schaufeli, W. B. , Leiter, M. P. , & Taris, T. W. . (2016). Work engagement: an emerging concept in occupational health psychology. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 187-200.
- Bo, C. L., & Xing, Z. M.. (2019). *Formation and change mechanism, evaluation methods and future prospects of non market value of professional sports teams*. Summary of theses of the 11th National Sports Science Conference.
- Brian, T., Gregory, M., & David, A.. (2010). Talai Osmonbekov. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, (25), 639-647.
- Briscoe, J. P., & Hall, D. T. (2015). The interplay of boundaryless and protean careers: Combinations and implications. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 69(1), 4-18.
- Cai, M.. (2020). Strategies for improving the effectiveness of Ideological and political work of young employees in state owned enterprises. *Modern enterprise*, 415(4), 102-103.
- Campbell, T. A.. (2014). What could have been done? circuit city: a case study of management and employee performance failure. *Performance Improvement*, 53(4), 16-23.
- Cao, X. G., Zhang, Y. F., & Wang, Y.. (2015). Integration of career management between self and organization. *Modern corporate culture*, (6), 98.
- Chen, C. H.. (2020). How to "people oriented" in modern enterprises. *China Development Observation*, 249(21), 47-48.
- Chen, J. H., & Bu, J. C.. (2016). Discussion on the stimulation of engagement based on the theory of employee needs. *Dossier*, (11), 230-231.
- Chen, M. S., & Shen, H. P.. (2015). An empirical study on the relationship between trust, engagement and work performance in an organization. *Financial theory and Practice*, (3), 113-118.
- Chen, M., & Peng, Z. Y.. (2011). Non profit organizations in Dunhuang accounting documents. *Journal of Hunan University of Finance and Economics*, 27(29), 34-36.
- Chen, S. L., & Shang, C. Y.. (2019). A study on the relationship between human capital and occupational adaptability of new generation employees. *Journal of Anhui University of Architecture*, 27(2), 103-109.
- Chen, T. T., Ye, Z., Zheng, S. P., Wang, X. Y., & Liu, X. Y.. (2021). Survey on job satisfaction and job burnout of family doctors in Putuo District of Shanghai. *Chinese Journal of general practitioners*, 20(2), 199-204.
- Chen, W. H.. (2012). On the development of Buddhist cultural tourism. *Fayin*, (11), 55-58.
- Chen, W. S., Liu, W. J., & Shen, J.. (2016). The direct and indirect influence of participatory management on the performance of new generation employees. *Human resource development in China*, (19), 99-107.
- Chen, X. P.. (2008). An empirical approach to organization and management research. *Peking University Business Review*, (7), 128.
- Chen, X. Y.. (2018). *A study of Buddhist six facet respectable harmony and its modern ethical value*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Christian, M. S. , Garza, A. S. , & Slaughter, J. E. . (2013). Work engagement: a quantitative review and test of its relations with task and contextual performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 64(1), 89-136.
- Chu, C. X., Mao, H. Q., & Jiang R. L.. (2012). The relationship among leadership behavior, organizational support and employee engagement: a case study of communication enterprises. *Journal of Beijing University of post and Telecommunications*, 14(5), 91-99.

- Chudzikowski, K. (2012). Career transitions and career Success in the 'new' career era. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 85(2), 298-306.
- Culbertson, S. S. , Mills, M. J. , & Fullagar, C. J. . (2014). Work engagement and work-family facilitation: making homes happier through positive affective spillover. *Human Relations*, 65(9), 1155-1177.
- David, S.. (2016). *Activation: let employees enjoy their work*. Beijing: China Renmin University Press.
- Deng, X. Y.. (2015). *This paper expounds the practical significance of carrying forward the sixth ancestor culture of Zen to realize the Chinese dream*. Symposium on folk intangible cultural heritage
- Ding, L. M.. (2011). The profit making behavior of non-profit organizations. *Commercial marketing*, (2), 5-7.
- Ding, X. L.. (2010). Management innovation is the new driving force for the survival and development of enterprises. *Brand*, (9), 39.
- Duan, C. X., & Li, C. X.. (2018). The effect of positive emotion on attention: Based on extended construction theory and motivation dimension theory. *Youth*, (16), 86-87.
- Eby, L.T., Butts, M., & Lockwood, A.. (2003). Predictors of Success in the Era of Boundaryless Careers. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24(5), 689-708.
- Feldman, D. C., & Ng, W. H.. (2007). Careers: Mobility, embeddedness, and success. *Journal of Management*, 33(3), 350-377.
- Fredrickson, B. L. , & Branigan, C. . (2016). Positive emotions broaden the scope of attention and thought` ction repertoires. *Cognition & Emotion*, 19(3), 313-332.
- Fredrickson, B. L. , & Losada, M. F. . (2016). The positive affect and the complex dynamics of human flourishing. *American Psychologist*, 60(7), 678-686.
- Gan, R. G.. (2015). On the influencing factors of the formation of employees' organizational management commitment from the perspective of social exchange theory. *Economic research reference*, (55), 87-89.
- Gao, X. M., Zhu, B., Du, J. J., & Li, Y. X.. (2020). The relationship between work family promotion and career success: the mediating role of psychological capital. *Chinese Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 28(01), 186-189.
- Gao, X. Y.. (2020). *Influencing factors and Countermeasures of nurses' job satisfaction from the perspective of career expectation*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Gao, Y. N., Wang, Y. F., & Wang, S. J.. (2020). The impact of career growth opportunities on employee engagement: the role of perceived organizational support and person job fit. *Fujian tea*, 42(2), 99-101.
- Gathoni, N. L.. (2012). *Perceived effect of performance management practices on employee satisfaction at Swedish Cooperative Centre*. Swedish Cooperative Centre.
- Greenhaus, J. H., Parasuraman, S., & Wormley, W. M.. (1990). Effects of Race on Organizational Experience, Job Performance Evaluation and Career Outcomes. *Academy of Management Journal*, (33), 64-86.
- Guo, E. C.. (2008). The key to effective management is to form "mechanism". *China Hi-tech Zone*, (6), 104-106.
- Halbesleben, J. R. B. , & Wheeler, A. R. . (2014). The relative roles of engagement and embeddedness in predicting job performance and intention to leave. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 242-256.
- Han, S., & Lian, C. D.. (2019). Research on the evaluation index system of College Students' career success. *Management and research of scientific and technological achievements*, (1), 39-42.
- Han, Y., Liao, J. Q., & Long, L. R. (2007). The construction and empirical study of employee performance structure model. *Journal of management science*, (5), 62-77.
- Harter, J. K. , Schmidt, F. L. , & Hayes, T. L. . (2002). Business-unit-level relationship between employee satisfaction, employee engagement, and business outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(2), 268-79.
- Harter, J. K. , Schmidt, F. L. , & Hayes, T. L. . (2014). Business-unit-level relationship between employee satisfaction, employee engagement, and business outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(2), 268-79.
- He, D.. (2020). *Performance management of CS commercial bank based on balanced scorecard*

- (Doctoral dissertation).
- He, S. H.. (2015). *Research on the relationship between engagement and job performance of sales staff in state owned enterprises*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Hong, S.. (2020). On the role of non profit organizations in public crisis management. *Economic Research Guide*, 456(34), 154-155.
- Hu, A. M.. (2012). The focus of China's pension service under the background of rapid aging -- from the perspective of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. *Journal of Fujian provincial Party School of CPC*, (12), 94-99.
- Hu, J. X.. (2015). Multi dimensional interpretation of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *Philosophical research*, (8), 104-108.
- Huang, D. J.. (2013). Research on the characteristics and optimization of human resource reward system in modern Tibetan temple economy. *Social Science*, (1), 76-77.
- Huang, L. T.. (2003). *Study on the specific index of nurses' professional personality*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Huang, X. N.. (2014). A study of "Chinese Buddhist Association". *Chinese Buddhism*, (2), 1-21.
- Huang, X.. (2019). The impact of career development opportunity perception on employee engagement in new generation enterprises. *Market Weekly*, (15), 139-143.
- Huang, Y., Yang, L. Z., Ye, F., & Xie, A. Z.. (2012). Application of satisfaction evaluation in hospital performance management -- Taking the First Affiliated Hospital of Guangxi Medical University as an example. *Economic and social development*, (11), 77-79.
- Huang, Z. G.. (2003). *Investigation, analysis and countermeasures on job satisfaction of knowledge workers in Xingma company*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Hunt, S. D., Chonko, L. B., & Wood, V. R.. (1986). Marketing Education and Marketing Success: Are they Related. *Journal of Education*, (2), 2-12.
- Jaksic, M.. (2013). Performance management and employee satisfaction. *Montenegrin Journal of Economics*, (9), 85-92.
- Ji, X. L., & Zhou, X. C.. (2012). Research on the relationship between the fit of strategic human resource management, the efficiency of human resource management and organizational performance of high tech Enterprises. *Soft Science*, (11), 99-104.
- Ji, Z. P.. (2020). Research on career management of knowledge workers in radio and television industry. *Fujian Quality Management*, (2), 136.
- Jia, M.. (2010). *Research on Influencing Factors of performance appraisal satisfaction of College Counselors in Xi'an*. (Doctoral dissertation, Xi'an: Xi'an University of Technology).
- Jiang, J. L.. (2015). The relationship between organizational culture and human resource management and their great role in the construction of organization. *Intelligence*, (30), 347-348.
- Jin, X. J., & Xiao, Z. X.. (2020). CEO career anxiety and peer effect in corporate investment strategy. *Journal of Zhejiang University*, 50(1), 98-119.
- Kahn, W. A.. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692 - 724.
- Klehe, U.C., Zikic, J., Vianen, A. E., & Pater, I. E.. (2013). Career adaptability, turnover and loyalty during organizational downsizing. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 79(1), 217-229.
- Kong, C., & Ding, X.. (2014). Research on reader satisfaction evaluation of University library based on confirmatory factor analysis. *Journal of Shanxi Library Science*, (5), 60-64.
- Kong, L. Y., & Kong, H. Y., & Bu, N. P.. (2019). Career management and career satisfaction: the mediating role of career expectation. *Modern management*, 9(4), 488-496.
- Li, G. R., Zhong, Y. M., Huang, Q., Liu, X. T., & Li, Y.. (2020). Mediating effect of self esteem on career identity and life meaning of medical students. *Medicine and society*, 33(7), 110-114.
- Li, H. M.. (2007). *Research on the satisfaction of Jiangmen town government staff performance appraisal*. (Doctoral dissertation, Guangzhou:South China Normal University).
- Li, J. P.. (2016). Focus on efficiency improvement, help strategic objectives -- Innovative Practice of performance management in state-owned service enterprises. *Youth*, (21), 228-229.
- Li, J.. (2020). The main problems and Countermeasures of enterprise staff evaluation. *Management and technology of small and medium sized enterprises*, (12), 131-132.

- Li, L. J.. (2019). *The influence of career adaptability on employees' initiative behavior*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Li, M. F... (2020). *Research on the influencing factors and improvement measures of employees' job satisfaction in y new materials company*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Li, X. Y., Yang, B. X., Jiang, L. P., Zuo, W. C., & Zhang, B. F.. (2018). Research on the relationship among job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention of early career employees. *China soft science*, (1), 163-170.
- Li, X. Y.. (2018). On the application strategy of emotional incentive in human resource management. *The age of intellectual wealth*, (2), 171.
- Li, Y. P., & Huang, Z. J.. (2017). The role of confirmatory factor analysis in the evaluation of the structure validity of the scale. *Public health in China*, (10), 1198-1199.
- Li, Y. Y., & Ding, H.. (2010). On the staff incentive mechanism based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. *Popular technology*, (9), 185.
- Li, Y. Y., & Gu. Y. F.. (2010). On the theory and practice of modern Buddhist temples -- Taking Hongfa temple in Shenzhen as an example. *Chinese Academy of Social Sciences*, (8), 30-33.
- Liang, Y.. (2015). The relationship between the satisfaction of employees of different levels of real estate enterprises to the performance management system of enterprises. *Human resource management*, (2), 96-97.
- Liu, F.. (2013). *Am company incentive mechanism optimization design scheme*. (Doctoral dissertation, Zhengzhou: Zhengzhou University).
- Liu, J. T.. (2018). *Strengthen the localized management of religious affairs in accordance with the law*. Collection of Papers of Benxi United Front Theory Research Association in 2018.
- Liu, J., Zhao, X. K., & Shen, H. L.. (2020). Is career planning beneficial to employees' innovative behavior? -- the mediating role of continuous learning and self-efficacy and the moderating role of organizational climate. *Forecast*, (4), 53-60.
- Liu, J.. (2015). Warren Bennis: subverting the leadership myth. *Operation and management*, (1), 12-13.
- Liu, L.. (2009). *Reflections on leadership*. Beijing: CITIC publishing house.
- Liu, X., & Yang, D. T.. (2017). Work autonomy and employee engagement: the moderating role of self-monitoring and distributive justice. *Business Economics and management*, 4(148), 42-49.
- Liu, Y. S., & Yang, M. H.. (2019). A study on the relationship between employees' leisure involvement and job satisfaction and job performance: the mediating variable of leisure benefit. *Journal of physical education of Chengdu University*, 51(1), 17-38.
- Long, L. R., & Mao, M. X.. (2007). A study on the relationship between self career management and career success. *Journal of management*, 4(3), 312.
- Luo, Q. M., & Feng, Q. H.. (2002). Business management in the era of knowledge economy. *Ningbo economy: a financial perspective*, (4), 35-36.
- Luo, W. H., Sun, Y. Q., Gao, F., Chen, J. Y., & Xiong, T. R.. (2020). 教 Research on the influence mechanism of practice leadership on employees' subjective career success. *Journal of management*, (7), 33-41.
- Ma, H. Y.. (2015). On the ways to cultivate professional interest. *Henan Education*, (7), 96-97.
- Ma, J. Z.. (2020). The relationship between leadership behavior and government performance: An Empirical Study Based on the mediating role of subordinate trust. *Journal of Shanghai Administration College*, 21(2), 36-46.
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P.. (1999). Burnout and engagement in the workplace : a contextual analysis. *Advances in Motivation and Achievement*, (11), 275 - 302.
- May ,D. R., Gilson ,R. L., & Harter, L.. (2004). The psychological conditions of meaningfulness, safety, and availability and the engagementof the human spirit at work. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 77(1), 11 - 37.
- Meyer, H.H., Kay, E., & French, J.R.. (1965). Split roles in performance appraisal. *Business Review*, (43), 123-129.
- Ming, S.. (2014). Buddhist charity in contemporary China. *Chinese religion*, (6), 50-52.
- Mishra, G., & Farooqi, R.. (2014). Exploring Employee Satisfaction With Performance Management and the Challenges Faced in Context of IT Industry, *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 45(6),

329-339.

- Motowidlo, S. J.. (1993). Evidence that task performance should be distinguished from contextual performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79(4), 475-480.
- Nigel, N., & Wendy, D. W.. (2005). Playing to win: Biological Imperatives, Self-Regulation and Trade-Offs in the Game of Career Success. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(2), 137-154.
- Niu, S.. (2009). *On the relationship between career adaptability and career success in the era of boundless career*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Obi, O. (2015). Constructionist career counseling of undergraduate students : An experimental *Evaluation Journal of Vocational Behavior*, (88), 215-219.
- Otieno, R. W.. (2010). *Performance management and employee satisfaction in Insurance Company of East Africa*. Kisumu branch:University of Nairobi Kenya.
- Pan, Z. H.. (2020). Innovation self efficacy and employee innovation performance: the moderating effect of internalized innovation role identity. *Quality and Market*, 271(20), 67-69.
- Paul, & Rich. (2006). Employee assistance programs: ensuring their continued value and viability. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, (1), 36-39.
- Prince, J.B., & Lawler, E. E.. (1986). Does salary discuss hurt the developmental performance appraisal, *Organizational Behavior and Human Resource Decision Processes*, (37), 375.
- Pu, S., Huang, X. T., Zhang, L. X., Wei, J. G., Yi, H. M., & Song, Y. Q.. (2016). The impact of vocational education on human capital development in developing countries: evidence from China. *World Bank Economic Review*, (1), P.170-204.
- Qiu, S. F.. (2016). *Research on the influencing factors of front line employees' engagement in star hotels -- Taking sense of belonging as the mediating variable*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Qiu, Y., Zhu, Q., & Shi, B. Y.. (2019). Research on the promotion strategy of employee loyalty based on job performance improvement. *Century Bridge*, 341(3), 89-90.
- Rao, X. L.. (2013). The application and Enlightenment of Maslow's hierarchy of human basic needs. *Chinese Journal of Modern Nursing*, 19(20), 2463-2465.
- Rothbard, N. P. , Dumas, T. L. , & Phillips, K. W. . (2001). The long arm of the organization: work-family policies, employee preferences for segmentation, and satisfaction and commitment. *Academy of Management Annual Meeting Proceedings*, (1), 1-6.
- Salanova, A. H., & Rehmat, K.. (2015). Impact of Core HR Practices on Employee Engagement, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 4(9), 68-73.
- Salanova, M. , Agut, S. , & José María Peiró. (2015). Linking organizational resources and work engagement to employee performance and customer loyalty: the mediation of service climate. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(6), 1217-1227.
- Savickas, M. L.. (2005). *The theory and practice of career construction, Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work*. Hoboken, New Jersey, US: John Wiley& Sons.
- Savickas, M. L. (2015). *Career construction theory and practice*. Hoboken, NJ, US: John Wiley& Sons.
- Savickas, M. L. , & Porfeli, E. J. (2015). Career adapt—abilities scale: Construction, reliability, and measurement equivalence across 13 countries. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 80(3). 661-673.
- Schaufeli, VV. B. , Salanova. M. , Gonzalez - Roma , V. , & Bakker, A. B..(2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71-92.
- Schaufeli, W. B. , Ouweneel, E. , Le Blanc, P. M. , & Wijhe, C. I. . (2012). Good morning, good day: a diary study on positive emotions, hope, and work engagement. *Human Relations*, 65(9), 1129-1154.
- Schaufeli, Wilmar, B. , Bakker, Arnold, B. , Salanova, & Marisa. (2006). The measurement of work engagement with a short questionnaire: a cross-national study. *Educational & Psychological Measurement*, (3), 69-77.
- Seibert, S. E., & Kraimer, M. L.. (2001). The Five-Factor Model of Personality and Career Success. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, (58), 1-21.
- Shao, D.. (2015). Research on performance management under the guidance of promoting employee initiative. *Business Manager*, (3), 185-186.

- Shen, Y.. (2018). *Research on employee engagement of DGL company*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Shi, K., Guo, H. D., & Liu, J. Y.. (2020). Research on structural dimensions and scale development of employees' job well being. *Journal of Sichuan University of light chemical industry*, 35(2), 7-23.
- Shi, Y.. (2020). Research on measures to improve the effectiveness of personnel incentive in human resource management. *Rural economy and science and technology*, 31(20), 179-180.
- Shu, X. L., Wang, N., & Ye, M. L.. (2019). The relationship between career adaptability, career satisfaction and job performance *Chinese Journal of mental health*, 33(1), 77-79.
- Tang, M. Y., Liang, Q. Z., & Zhang, J.. (2015). *Personality differences and perceived organizational support: the mediating role of leader member exchange*. China Management Modernization Research Association, Ministry of education.
- Tang, T., Li, P., Sarsfield, N. & Linda, J.. (1996), Distributive and procedural justice as related to satisfaction and commitment. *Advanced Management Journal*, (61), 25-27.
- Tao, J. H., & Zhao, Y.. (2019). Employees' feedback seeking behavior and their career success: the intermediary of self efficacy. *Enterprise economy*, (7), 129-135.
- Thorndike, E. L. . (1943). The prediction of success in vocational life. *The Vocational Guidance Magazine*, (1), 12.
- Tian, M.. (2020). On the international comparison of social assistance financing and fund management mode in the new era. *Operator*, 4(9), 32,34.
- Tian, Y.. (2019). On the application of employee motivation in small and medium enterprises. *Labor security world*, 531(11), 12-13.
- Tu, Y. D.. (2015). *Research on employee organization relationship from the perspective of social exchange and social identity*. Wuhan: Wuhan University Press.
- Tusi, D. S., Lucas, V. A., Simone, C. N., & Julio, C. M.. (1997). Estimation of stochastic frontier cost efficiency for companies in the electricity distribution sector. *Federal Institute of Technology*, 39(1), 221-247.
- Vegchel, N. V. , Jonge, J. D. , Bakker, A. B. , & Schaufeli, W. B.. (2002). Testing global and specific indicators of rewards in the effort-reward imbalance model: does it make a difference?. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 11(4).
- Wagner. (1994). Participation's effects on performance and satisfaction: A reconsideration of research evidence. *The Academy of Management Review*, (19), 312-319.
- Wang, B. C., & Ding, H.. (2012). Research on the influence of employee performance appraisal methods on organizational performance. *Enterprise economy*, (3), 98-101.
- Wang, C. C., & Fu, C. X.. (2015). Research on interpersonal relationship of College Students' dormitory from the perspective of social exchange theory. *Journal of Chifeng University*, (4), 223-224.
- Wang, C. P.. (2015). *Research on the relationship between job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior based on the mediating effect of job satisfaction*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Wang, D.. (2016). Building a boundless stage for employees -- human resource management of Dow Chemical. *Human Resources*, (8), 10-19.
- Wang, G. Y.. (2007). An analysis of employee satisfaction in performance management of state owned Enterprises -- Taking NADA company as an example. *Guangxi Light Industry*, (9), 23-27.
- Wang, H.. (2018). The innovation of human resource management system in colleges and universities based on competency. *Management and technology of small and medium sized enterprises*, (10), 23-24.
- Wang, J. J., & Zhang, Y. L.. (2015). Research on employee performance management satisfaction. *Accounting news*, (11), 54-57.
- Wang, J., Zhang, Q. Y., Chen, H. Q., Sun, D. Y., Wang, C., & Liu, X. M.. (2020). Development of core occupational stress scale for Chinese occupational population. *Chinese Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 54(11), 1184-1189.
- Wang, P.. (2008). *Investigation and analysis on the satisfaction degree of performance appraisal of teaching staff in local normal universities*. (Doctoral dissertation, Beijing: Beijing Renmin University).
- Wang, S. L..王胜利. (2015). *Research on measurement of satisfaction degree of enterprise performance management*. (Doctoral dissertation, Yunnan: Yunnan University).

- Wang, W., Jiang, H. Z., & Xv, W. X.. (2016). *An empirical study on the impact of job satisfaction and engagement on employee performance -- Based on SG group*. Annual conference of Chinese Management -- collection of essays of the branch of organizational behavior and human resource management.
- Wang, X. C., & Hao, X. N., Wu, Y. H., Yang, Q., Qiu, D. X., Li, S. X., & Mai, Y. B.. (2013). Research on the status quo of employees' satisfaction with performance management in community health service institutions. *General practice in China*, (21), 1841-1843.
- Wang, X. P.. (2016). The relationship between human capital, job characteristics and income satisfaction of scientific and technological talents in Enterprises. *Ergonomics*, 22(2), 36-42.
- Wang, X.. (2017). *The mechanism of organizational developmental support on turnover intention of knowledge workers*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Wang, Y. Q.. (2016). *Rethinking Maslow's theory of self actualization*. Symposium on exploration science.
- Wang, Z. J., & Long, L. R.. (2005). On the relationship between social capital and career success in the era of knowledge economy, *Foreign economy and management*, 27(2), 18-24.
- Wang, Z. J., & Long, L. R.. (2009), Employees' career success: the influence mechanism and explanatory effect of social capital, *Management review*, 21(8), 30-39.
- Wang, Z. Y.. (2018). The research on the influencing factors and countermeasures of the employee's work input. *New business weekly*, (2), 67-73.
- Wen, Z. Y.. (2005). Four factor structure model of job performance, *Journal of Capital Normal University*, (5), 105-111.
- Weng, Q. X., Peng, C. H., Cao, W. L., & Xi, Y. M.. (2016). The relationship between Big Five personality and subjective career success: a meta analysis of the past 15 years. *Management review*, (1), 83-95.
- Wu, J. H., Zhao, B. Q., & Wang, L.. (2008). *An empirical study on the impact of performance management cognition on the engagement of middle level cadres in Colleges and Universities*. Proceedings of the third (2008) annual meeting of China management. China Management Modernization Research Association.
- Wu, J.. (2019). Achievements, problems and reform path of Vocational Education in the new era: Based on the interpretation of the report of the 19th CPC National Congress. *Guangzhou Vocational Education Forum*, 18(1), 55-62.
- Wu, M. L.. (2010). *Practice of questionnaire statistical analysis: operation and application of SPSS*. Chongqing: Chongqing University Press.
- Wu, S. M.. (2020). Research on the importance of human resource management in Enterprises. *Economics*, 3(4), 55-56.
- Wu, X. J., Zhang, G. Y., & Guo, J.. (2018). An empirical study on the influence of human capital on promotion speed. *Commercial economy*, (10), 83-86.
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., & Llies, R.. (2012). Everyday working life: explaining within-person fluctuations in employee well-being. *Human Relations*, 65(9), 1051-1069.
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B.. (2009). Work engagement and financial returns: a diary study on the role of job and personal resources. *Journal of Occupational & Organizational Psychology*, 82(1), 183-200.
- Xia, H. J., Li, G. Q., Ji, P., & Liu, S.. (2020). The impact of interpersonal social support on employees' innovative behavior and job performance: the mediating effect of individual environment fit. *Modern management*, 10(2), 269-278.
- Xia, Y. Y.. (2014). Research on employee satisfaction of performance management of Anhui HL group. *Journal of Hubei University of Economics*, (5), 55-57.
- Xian, X. Z.. (2012). *Research on property management of Buddhist temples in Guangdong rural areas (1978-2000)*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Xiao, F. B.. (2020). *Research on the influence of colleague relationship and system effectiveness on employees' work quality*. (Doctoral dissertation).
- Xin, Y. R., & Yang, L.. (2020). The influence of job remodeling intervention on employees' career management. *Knowledge Economy*, (8), 22,24.
- Xue, Y. X.. (2019). Literature review of employee engagement. *Fujian Quality Management*, (7), 63.

- Xv, B., Huang, C. X., & Wu, X. Y.. (2015). Investigation and analysis of hospital staff's satisfaction with performance management. *Hospital Management Forum*, (8), 52-55.
- Yan, J.. (2018). The development of Chinese Buddhism in the past 40 years since the reform and opening up. *Chinese Religion*, 228(11), 28-30.
- Yan, W. H., Yu, G. T., & Lin, L.. (2018). The influence of career adaptability on subjective career success: the mediating role of job shaping and the moderating role of organizational support. *Economic management*, 40(8), 105-119.
- Yan, Y.. (2020). Starting from respect, unconditional acceptance and care. *Doctor Online*, 10(12), 46-47.

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